

DEVELOPMENT OF A SWR METER USING MICROSTRIP LINES

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Abstract – This paper presents, in a summarized manner, the development and simulation of a standing wave ratio meter using the Quite Universal Circuit Simulator Studio (QucsStudio) software. The selected substrate for the project was FR-4.

Keywords: Standing wave ratio meter; QucsStudio; FR-4.

INTRODUCTION

Wireless transmissions are of great importance in various areas of development. Antennas form the basis of wireless transmissions [1]. For optimal performance of these antennas, impedance matching is necessary. In a real scenario, there is a possibility of energy transfer problem between the line and the antenna [2]. Standing wave refers to the periodic oscillation that occurs in propagated frequency waves. An alternative, with excellent cost-effectiveness, is the use of standing wave ratio meters.

Figure 1 – Printed circuit SWR meter

The device under analysis was developed based on a model [5], using the QucsStudio software.

DEVELOPMENT

Parameters were inserted to study the circuit behavior across the range of 120 MHz to 500 MHz. In addition to the behavior, the main characteristic of this device was also observed: the impedance matching verification within a range of 0 to 100Ω through Rsweep (device output). With that said, P1 (device input) is considered as another device (such as a coaxial cable) with 50Ω impedance. The circuit compares, among the given frequencies and the impedances of Rsweep, where the best impedance match with P1 occurs.

Directional couplers must fulfill another characteristic of an SWR meter: the transmission line must have a null external field [3]. In other words, the diode of each directional coupler needs to be biased in a way that only signals occurring in one direction are measured. One diode is responsible for the reflection half-cycle (vref), and the other is responsible for the incident (v fwd) signals.

Figure 2 – SWR meter circuit in QucsStudio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the parameters presented in the previous figure, the simulation was performed. At the end of it, the following diagram was obtained:

Figure 3 – SWR meter circuit in QucsStudio

Observing the diagram, it is noticeable that the VSWR is low when Rsweep is equal to 50Ω. It is also noted that the VSWR increases as Rsweep deviates from 50Ω because this is the value present at P1, indicating optimal impedance matching. Finally, it can be observed that when attempting a match with 0Ω, the VSWR assumes extremely high values. This occurs because all the signal being sent ends up being reflected back to the source P1 (damaging the entire circuit). Lastly, another point to highlight is that,

regardless of Rsweep, the VSWR increases throughout the frequency range. According to the found table [4], it is confirmed that the impedance matching with Rsweep of 50Ω falls within an ideal range.

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